

Physics-Informed Effectiveness Indicators for Whole-building Evaluation of Phase Change Materials in Buildings

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Abstract

Phase change materials (PCMs) are a promising passive technology for reducing building heating and cooling energy use, yet their whole-building effectiveness as latent thermal storage remains insufficiently characterized. The present study introduces PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs)—a set of physics-informed, whole-building metrics that relate daily thermal-load reductions to the installed latent heat capacity. The proposed indicators capture dynamic, year-round performance across climates, implicitly accounting for partial phase transitions, fluctuating loads, and interactions with passive design strategies. They can be applied consistently to heating, cooling, and mixed-load analyses. Using EnergyPlus simulations and a global sensitivity analysis, 400 design configurations were evaluated for a prototype building in four ASHRAE climate zones (3A, 4A, 5A, and 6A). Across all climates, envelope characteristics, particularly the window-to-wall ratio, exerted a stronger influence on PCM effectiveness than commonly studied material properties such as melting temperature. These findings highlight the importance of co-optimizing PCMs with envelope design variables, especially at early design stages. Furthermore, PCMs achieved the highest effectiveness in heating-dominated climates and when mitigating cooling loads. Despite substantial PCM-induced load reductions, PCMEI values rarely exceeded 20%, indicating practical limits to whole-building latent-capacity utilization under real climatic variability. A design threshold was identified: maintaining installed latent heat capacity below approximately twice the building's peak daily thermal load prevents oversizing and maximizes utilization. The proposed PCMEIs provide a transparent and scalable framework for whole-building evaluation of PCMs, supporting benchmark development and performance-based integration in energy-efficient building design.

Keywords: Phase change materials, Whole-building performance, Building energy modeling, Thermal energy storage, Passive design strategies.

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1. Introduction

The building sector accounts for more than one-third of global energy consumption and nearly 30% of total energy-related emissions [1]. Decarbonizing this sector is therefore crucial to achieving the climate goals set by the Paris Agreement [2], which aims to limit global warming to below 1.5–2°C above pre-industrial levels. Reducing energy consumption in buildings while maintaining thermal comfort is essential for addressing climate change and mitigating the impacts of extreme weather events [3, 4].

Among the various technologies available to improve building energy efficiency, phase change materials (PCMs) have gained attention due to their ability to store and release substantial amounts of heat during phase transitions. PCMs operate within a narrow temperature range in which their *specific heat capacity* (c_p , $\text{J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) appears to increase sharply, as shown in Fig. 1. This apparent variation does not represent a discontinuity in material properties but reflects the combined sensible and latent heat exchange that occurs during melting and solidification. By harnessing this thermophysical behavior, PCMs can be incorporated into building components to reduce thermal loads for cooling [5, 6] and heating [7, 8], stabilize indoor temperatures [9], and enhance overall building energy performance [10].

Fig. 1: Variation of the specific heat capacity of a phase change material (PCM) as a function of temperature. The curve highlights the apparent increase near the melting temperature due to the latent-heat storage effect occurring in the two-phase region.

Despite their potential, the successful implementation of PCMs in buildings depends on daily thermal cycles. Without proper design considerations, PCMs may not deliver the expected benefits and could even lead to undesirable thermal effects. Key design parameters include thermophysical properties, PCM quantity, and placement within the building envelope (e.g., ceiling, walls, and solar orientations) [11].

Two primary approaches are used to assess PCM impacts in buildings. The first involves experimental testing or field monitoring, where physical mock-ups or full-scale buildings incorporating PCMs are analyzed [12, 13]. While reliable, this approach is costly and limited in evaluating PCM performance under long-term and varied climate conditions. The second approach relies on building performance simulations [9, 14, 15], which model PCM-integrated buildings to predict their effects on indoor temperatures, energy consumption, and other performance metrics. Whole-building simulation tools [16] are preferable

over component-based methods, as they better capture the interactions between PCMs and other building dynamics. Simulations also enable sensitivity analyses [17] and optimization studies [18].

Various criteria have been proposed to evaluate PCM performance. Some researchers [19–21] use simplified metrics, such as peak temperature reduction and time lag between indoor and outdoor temperature maxima. However, these indicators are insufficient for assessing long-term PCM benefits. A more comprehensive approach involves using building performance indicators such as energy consumption and thermal comfort.

For instance, Saffari et al. [22] optimized PCM melting temperatures in a multi-family building by minimizing annual energy consumption under different climate conditions. Cascone et al. [9] considered energy consumption and costs to optimize PCM thickness and thermophysical properties in office buildings. Wang et al. [23] conducted a parametric study to identify optimal PCM configurations for reducing air conditioning demand and improving indoor comfort in a high-rise office building in Shanghai, China.

While these methods provide valuable insights, quantifying PCM effectiveness remains challenging. Different PCM designs may yield similar energy savings but require significantly different PCM amounts, affecting cost-effectiveness. Due to the low thermal conductivity of PCMs [24–26], increasing PCM volume enhances latent storage capacity, yet a substantial portion may remain unutilized. Thus, a clear distinction is needed between PCM impact (e.g., energy savings) and PCM effectiveness (i.e., performance impact relative to the quantity of PCM installed). Given the high cost of PCMs, avoiding excessive use is essential to prevent economic inefficiencies and rebound effects.

Despite extensive research, only a few studies have proposed indicators to quantify PCM effectiveness. Sun et al. [27] introduced an energy and mass efficiency indicator to evaluate PCM boards in office buildings across different climates, considering natural cold energy utilization and stored energy usage. However, this approach is specific to cooling applications and does not account for overall building performance. Bhamare et al. [28] proposed a unique index, the Measure of Key Response (MKR) index, for selecting the optimum phase change material to enhance the thermal performance of building envelopes. This index allows for a comparative evaluation between a PCM-integrated roof and a non-PCM roof based on parameters such as time lag, decrement factor, and total heat gain from the roof surface. The approach proposed by these authors is important as it compares the relative performance between scenarios with and without PCM. However, it lacks a relative evaluation regarding the amount of PCM required to achieve the relative improvement. Moreover, most of these approaches focus on individual building components (e.g., solely roof or wall) rather than whole-building performance, highlighting the need for comprehensive indicators.

Evola et al. [29] addressed this gap by introducing two indicators to assess PCM effectiveness through whole-building simulations. The first, Frequency of Activation, quantifies the percentage of time PCMs undergo phase transitions. However, this measure is more qualitative than quantitative, as activation does not necessarily translate to energy savings or improved comfort. A crucial factor not represented by this indicator is the variation in the specific heat capacity (c_p) of the PCM during phase transitions. In practical terms, the specific heat of the solid and liquid phases is considered constant, whereas within the two-phase region the material simultaneously stores sensible and latent heat. This combined effect is commonly represented in building-energy models by an equivalent, temperature-dependent c_p peak centered around the melting tem-

perature, which captures the latent-heat contribution without requiring explicit tracking of the solid–liquid interface. Consequently, the effective storage capacity increases near the peak phase-change temperature compared to the onset temperature, leading to the observed fluctuation in energy storage despite activation (see Fig. 1). This treatment is consistent with the enthalpy-based formulation implemented in EnergyPlus and other simulation tools.

The second indicator proposed by Evola et al. [29], PCM Storage Efficiency, measures the daily utilization of latent storage capacity by calculating the ratio of actual thermal energy stored to maximum capacity. While it provides a physics-based interpretation of PCM behavior, its limitations include the lack of direct correlation with energy savings or thermal comfort improvements, particularly when PCMs are positioned externally, where heat cycling may not benefit indoor conditions. Additionally, this indicator is mainly applicable to cooling applications, excluding heating scenarios and overall performance assessments, and requires improvements in computational complexity for practical implementation.

Despite the wide range of existing approaches, current PCM evaluation methods remain limited in three key ways: (1) they often focus on individual components rather than whole-building performance, (2) they do not consistently relate energy savings to the amount of PCM used, and (3) many indicators are either qualitative or computationally complex. As a result, there is a lack of general, physics-informed indicators that can reliably quantify PCM effectiveness across heating, cooling, and annual scenarios in a practical and scalable manner.

This study addresses this gap by introducing a set of novel PCM effectiveness indicators (PCMEIs) that integrate building performance outcomes with the quantity of PCM installed. In contrast to existing methods that focus solely on phase change activity or stored energy, the proposed indicators provide a physically grounded, simulation-friendly framework for assessing PCM effectiveness in heating, cooling, and combined applications. Additionally, the PCMEIs simplify computation and enhance applicability, enabling practical, year-round evaluation of PCM performance across diverse building designs and climates. These indicators can support multi-objective design strategies and inform early-stage decision-making for more cost-effective and thermally efficient PCM integration in buildings.

2. PCM Effectiveness Indicators

Fig. 2(a) illustrates the daily thermal load dynamics of a conditioned building, providing the physical basis for introducing the proposed PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs). The primary function of passive PCMs in buildings is to attenuate indoor thermal loads—heating, cooling, or total—and consequently reduce the demand on the heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system. In an idealized scenario, where the PCM undergoes complete melting and solidification cycles each day and maintains perfect thermal exchange with indoor air, a material with sufficient latent storage capacity to match the peak daily load could theoretically eliminate the corresponding annual heating or cooling demand. In practice, such performance is unattainable due to dynamic indoor temperature variations, seasonal changes in climatic conditions, and the finite rate of heat transfer between the PCM and the surrounding environment.

Fig. 2: Schematic representation of daily thermal loads and PCM operation in a conditioned building. (a) Schematic heating and cooling load profile relative to the HVAC comfort setpoints over a 24-hour cycle; (b) PCM acting as a thermal battery, absorbing heat during the day (melting) and releasing it at night (solidifying).

In this context, indicators for quantifying PCM effectiveness are essential for evaluating their thermal behavior in buildings and advancing PCM design and research to maximize their benefits. As previously discussed, a whole-building-level PCM effectiveness indicator should account not only for the physical behavior of PCMs (e.g., temperature variations) but also for their relative impact on building performance, such as energy consumption. Additionally, the indicator should account for the thermal latent capacity required to achieve these benefits. Moreover, an ideal indicator should be applicable to various PCM uses in buildings, including heating, cooling, and total load reduction.

To address these requirements, we propose a novel PCM effectiveness indicator (PCMEI), defined as:

$$\text{PCMEI} = \frac{100\% \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \text{DLS}(i)}{\text{TND} \cdot \text{LSC}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\text{DLS}(i)$ represents the daily load saved (kJ) by the incorporation of PCMs into the building, and LSC is the latent heat storage capacity (kJ) installed in the building using PCMs. TND is the total number of days with thermal loads. For annual studies, $n = 365$.

The PCMEI can be calculated for total loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Total}}$), heating loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Heating}}$), and cooling loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Cooling}}$). Since the thermal performance of PCMs in heating and cooling applications is typically

contradictory, it is advisable to calculate and analyze these separately.

The daily loads saved, $DLS(i)$, by the incorporation of PCMs into the building are calculated as:

$$DLS(i) = DL_{\text{Baseline}}(i) - DL_{\text{PCM}}(i), \quad (2)$$

where DL_{PCM} represents the daily loads (kJ) obtained through simulation or experimental results for the building design incorporating PCMs, and DL_{Baseline} represents the daily loads (kJ) for the same building design but without PCMs. This approach allows the analysis of the impact of variations in other building features or passive strategies on the effectiveness of PCMs.

The total number of days with thermal loads ($TND = \sum_{i=1}^n ND(i)$) must consider whether either the Baseline or PCM case has thermal loads. It is calculated as follows:

$$ND(i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } DL_{\text{Baseline}}(i) > \text{Tol or } DL_{\text{PCM}}(i) > \text{Tol} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $\text{Tol} = 0.1$ kWh is suggested to avoid counting numerical-noise days.

Finally, the latent heat storage capacity (LSC) installed in the building using PCMs is calculated as:

$$LSC = \sum_{j=1}^N m_{\text{PCM}_j} \Delta h_{\text{PCM}_j} \quad (3)$$

where m_{PCM_j} is the mass (kg) of the PCM_j , and Δh_{PCM_j} is the specific latent heat storage capacity (kJ/kg) of the PCM_j .

Interpretation of PCMEI values. As formulated, the PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs) estimate the ratio between the PCM-driven thermal load reductions and the installed latent heat storage capacity in the building. By definition, PCMEIs have a maximum theoretical value of 100%, representing an idealized condition in which the PCM capacity is fully and effectively utilized throughout the year—i.e., the daily reduction in thermal loads equals the installed latent capacity on every day with a thermal demand.

In practice, this level of performance is unattainable due to inherent physical and operational constraints, such as partial phase-change cycles, temperature mismatches between the PCM and indoor conditions, and incomplete charge–discharge processes. Moreover, daily and seasonal variations in thermal loads (Fig. 3) further limit continuous utilization of the PCM capacity.

Typically, PCMEI values are expected to be positive, indicating a net improvement in building performance resulting from PCM integration. Negative values may occur when PCM inclusion adversely affects performance—for instance, through inappropriate melting temperatures or poor thermal coupling—while zero values denote negligible impact, meaning that PCM-enhanced and baseline designs exhibit identical thermal loads over a given period.

Building thermal demands are inherently dynamic, varying by climate, occupancy, and internal heat gains. As illustrated in Fig. 3, these loads fluctuate across multiple timescales: (a)–(c) show annual daily heating, cooling, and total loads, emphasizing seasonal variation and long-term trends; (d)–(f) depict representative

hourly profiles for three characteristic days—a heating-dominated winter day, a cooling-dominated summer day, and a mixed-load transitional day (spring or autumn). These examples highlight that building thermal behavior is rarely uniform: some days exhibit single-direction loads, while others require simultaneous or alternating heating and cooling.

Fig. 3: Thermal load profiles in a conditioned building. (a)–(c) Annual daily heating, cooling, and total loads, respectively. (d)–(f) Hourly load profiles for a heating-only day (winter), a cooling-only day (summer), and a mixed-load day (transitional season), highlighting the variability of thermal demands throughout the year.

Generalization to multi-zone buildings. The PCMEI formulation presented above is readily extendable to multi-zone buildings. In such cases, each thermal zone may exhibit distinct thermal loads, PCM configu-

rations, and activation profiles. To account for this, the daily load savings and latent storage capacity must be computed independently for each zone, along with the total number of days with thermal loads (TND_z). The multi-zone PCMEI can thus be defined as:

$$PCMEI_{\text{multi-zone}} = \frac{100\% \cdot \sum_{z=1}^Z \sum_{i=1}^{n_z} DLS_z(i)}{\sum_{z=1}^Z TND_z \cdot LSC_z}, \quad (4)$$

where Z is the number of thermal zones, $DLS_z(i)$ is the daily load saved in zone z on day i , LSC_z is the latent heat storage capacity installed in zone z , and TND_z is the number of days with thermal load in zone z . This formulation preserves the physics-based consistency of the indicator while allowing for accurate performance assessment across spatially diverse buildings. It also enables zone-level comparisons and supports applications in complex, high-mass, or asymmetrically conditioned buildings.

3. Application of the PCM Effectiveness Indicators

This section presents a demonstrative case study to illustrate the practical application of the proposed PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs). The analysis serves two main purposes: (1) to demonstrate the step-by-step implementation of the indicators within a building performance simulation framework, and (2) to identify the design parameters that most strongly influence PCM effectiveness. To this end, a global sensitivity analysis was conducted, evaluating the impact of both material-related and building-envelope variables on PCM performance.

3.1. Case study building

A rectangular single zone (8 m wide x 6 m long x 2.7 m high) with no interior partitions and a window on the south exposure was employed to evaluate the thermal performance of the different design variable configurations in the sensitivity analysis; see Fig. 4.

The building energy model was implemented in the software EnergyPlus [30] - version 23.2. A power of 200 W (60% radiative, and 40% convective) was set as the internal load, and a highly insulated slab was employed to minimize the thermal coupling between the ground and indoors. The construction characteristics of the walls for the Baseline model are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Wall characteristics of the building case study.

Element	k [W/(m·K)]	Thickness [m]	R [(K·m ²)/W]	Density [kg/m ³]	c_p (sensible) [J/(kg·K)]
Int. Surface Coeff.			0.121		
Foam Insulation	0.04	<i>variable</i>	1.537	10	1400
Wood Siding	0.14	0.0090	0.064	530	900
Ext. Surface Coeff.			0.034		
Overall, air-to-air			1.952		

To study and generalize the conclusions about the proposed PCMEI, the simulations were performed in four well-representative locations—Capo Pertusato (France, 3A – Warm–humid), Osijek (Croatia, 4A – Mixed), Toruń (Poland, 5A – Cool), and Kongsvinger (Norway, 6A – Cold)—as defined in our previous

Fig. 4: Geometry of the case study building and configuration details of the roof and wall assemblies for the Baseline and PCM-enhanced models. PCM layers are applied to internal surfaces to evaluate their impact on thermal performance.

work [18]. These locations were identified as representative centroids for the main ASHRAE 169–2020 [31] climate zones within the WMO Region VI (Europe), following the clustering and validation procedure detailed by Bre et al. [18].

For each representative climate, the recent Typical Meteorological Year (TMYx 2009–2023) datasets [32] were used to compute the annual heating and cooling loads of the reference building. An ideal HVAC system was assumed, maintaining thermostat setpoints of 20°C for heating and 27°C for cooling. This configuration isolates the envelope-driven effects of PCM integration by eliminating dependencies on HVAC technology, part-load efficiency, or control strategies. Ideal loads represent the zone thermal balance required to maintain the prescribed indoor temperatures and thus provide a consistent, technology-neutral baseline for assessing PCM-induced load modulation. This approach not only enables direct comparison across climates and design scenarios but also supports the potential coupling of PCMEI-based analyses with thermal comfort models, since zone thermal balance calculations form the basis of common comfort indices (e.g., operative temperature, PMV, and PPD). While the ideal-load framework does not capture actual HVAC energy use, it preserves the physical link between envelope performance and indoor comfort, allowing future studies to integrate PCM effectiveness with comfort-oriented metrics and realistic HVAC operation.

Table 2 summarizes the main meteorological indicators for the four selected representative locations. The selection spans a broad climatic spectrum—from warm-humid (3A) to cold (6A)—ensuring that both heating- and cooling-dominated conditions are included in the analysis and that the derived conclusions can be generalized beyond a single-climate case.

Table 2: Summary of main meteorological information for the four representative climate locations (TMYx 2009–2023) [18, 32].

Climate zone	Representative location	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation [m]	CDD ₁₀ [°C]	HDD ₁₈ [°C]	Dominant regime
3A	Capo Pertusato (France)	N 41°22.5'	E 9°10.7'	116	2464	1116	Cooling-dominated (warm-humid)
4A	Osijek (Croatia)	N 45°27.8'	E 18°48.6'	88	1964	2502	Mixed heating/cooling
5A	Toruń (Poland)	N 53°3.0'	E 18°35.0'	72	1027	3499	Heating-dominated (cool)
6A	Kongsvinger (Norway)	N 60°11.4'	E 12°0.4'	148	614	4498	Heating-dominated (cold)

3.2. Implementation of the sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify which design variables most strongly influence the proposed PCM effectiveness indicators and to better understand the relationship between model inputs and outputs [33]. The Morris method [34] was adopted because it provides reliable global sensitivity rankings with relatively low computational cost compared to variance-based methods [35]. The analysis was implemented through the Python *Sensitivity Analysis Library* (SALib) [36, 37], which offers a robust and reproducible framework for sampling and post-processing.

In the EnergyPlus model, a set of seven design variables was defined to evaluate their influence on PCM performance. Two PCMs are incorporated—one in the internal side of the roof (PCM2) and one in the walls (PCM1), as illustrated in Fig. 4. The first four variables describe PCM-related properties: the thicknesses (THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}) and melting temperatures ($\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$ and $\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$). Three additional variables represent envelope design characteristics that can affect PCM activation: the insulation thickness of the walls (THK_{INS}), the window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and the normalized external shading length (ESR).

Therefore, seven design variables ($k = 7$) were analyzed, and four discrete levels are defined within their domain ranges, as summarized in Table 3. Following the procedure described in [34], the Morris method evaluates r random trajectories in the k -dimensional input space, each containing $(k + 1)$ sample points. The total number of simulations is therefore $r(k + 1)$. In this study, we use a Morris screening with $r = 50$ trajectories and $k = 7$ factors, yielding $r(k + 1) = 50 \times (7 + 1) = 400$ annual simulations *with PCM*. For each sampled design, we run a matched baseline by removing the PCM layers while keeping the same geometry and envelope parameters (THK_{INS} , WWR, ESR), adding another 400 runs. Per climate, this gives 800 simulations (400 PCM + 400 baseline), for a total of 3,200 simulations across the four climates analyzed.

Table 3: Building and PCM design variables were employed in the sensitivity analysis.

#	Design variable	ID	Unit	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
1	Thickness of PCM1 (walls)	THK_{PCM1}	m	0.005	0.020	0.035	0.050
2	Thickness of PCM2 (roof)	THK_{PCM2}	m	0.005	0.020	0.035	0.050
3	Peak melting temperature of PCM1 (walls)	$\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$	°C	20.5	22.5	24.5	26.5
4	Peak melting temperature of PCM2 (roof)	$\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$	°C	20.5	22.5	24.5	26.5
5	Thickness of insulation in the walls	THK_{INS}	m	0.050	0.083	0.117	0.150
6	Window-to-wall ratio	WWR	%	30	50	70	90
7	External shading ratio (shading length/height of window)	ESR	%	0	34	67	100

3.3. Parameterization of the design variables

In this section, the implementation of the design variables is described in detail. The research dataset for all the EnergyPlus models generated in this work is also openly available in [43] to facilitate the understanding of the implementation and reproduction of the results.

PCMs. Two different models of PCMs, one for each PCM layer, were implemented and parametrized in EnergyPlus. These were implemented using the single curve model (MaterialProperty:PhaseChange), whose accuracy has been widely validated regarding experimental results and analytical solutions [38–40]. The main input required for this model is the PCM enthalpy curve as a function of temperature, which can be described by up to 16 points of data. The conduction finite difference (CondFD) solution algorithm and 30 time-steps per hour are employed to guarantee accurate results, as recommended in [38].

The thicknesses of these PCM layers were directly parameterized in each model. Regarding the peak melting temperatures of PCMs, the model proposed by Feustel [41] was implemented and employed to parameterize them. This model describes the enthalpy of PCMs through a hyperbolic tangent function as:

$$h(T) = c_p T + \frac{\Delta h}{2} \left\{ 1 + \tanh \left[\frac{2\beta}{\tau} (T - T_{\text{peak}}) \right] \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where c_p is the specific sensible heat capacity in $\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$; T is the temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$; Δh is the specific latent heat storage capacity in J kg^{-1} ; $\beta = 1.4$ is the inclination constant controlling the curve symmetry; τ is the *temperature phase-transition interval* (in $^\circ\text{C}$), which defines the width of the two-phase region in which the PCM simultaneously stores sensible and latent heat. Smaller τ values correspond to a sharper transition between solid and liquid phases, whereas larger τ values yield a more gradual enthalpy change; and T_{peak} is the peak melting temperature.

Therefore, to set the main parameters of the model in Eq. 5, the properties of Rubitherm PCMs from the RTHC line [42] were employed. Table 4 lists the parameters used to configure Eq. 5 and the PCM model implemented in EnergyPlus. In this work, the parameter τ was fixed at 1°C to represent an *idealized phase-transition interval*, which assumes a sharp solid–liquid transition. The remaining parameters correspond to typical values of commercially available PCMs, ensuring that the resulting enthalpy–temperature behavior remains representative of real materials. In the present study, only the *melting temperature* and the *PCM mass* were varied, as these are the two parameters most widely investigated in building-scale PCM research and they exert the strongest influence on whole-building-level performance metrics. Fig. 5(a) illustrates example enthalpy curves for the four T_{peak} levels employed in the sensitivity analysis (see Table 3).

Table 4: Parameters were employed in the PCM modeling. Note that the density ρ and thermal conductivity k are also required to model PCMs in EnergyPlus.

Parameter	c_p [J/(kg-K)]	Δh [J/kg]	τ [$^\circ\text{C}$]	β [-]	ρ [kg/m ³]	k [W/(m-K)]
Value	2000	210000	1	1.4	880	0.2

Window. The WWR was calculated as the ratio between the window area and the area of the wall that contains it (i.e., the south wall). The parameterization of the WWR was performed using the object “Window” of EnergyPlus, which allows defining the size of the window by a starting point and the height and width of the window. To implement it, a fixed window width of 7.9 m was employed, while the window height was modified according to the resulting value to comply with the WWR.

External shading. The external shading device was implemented using the object “Shading:Overhang:Projection” of EnergyPlus. Through this, a perpendicular (i.e., tilt angle regarding the window = 90°) shading was defined at the top of the window, whose width is 8 m (as the building), and its depth was parameterized as the fraction of the window height. Figs. 5(b)–(d) show three combination examples for the WWR and ESR.

Fig. 5: Parameterization examples for T_{peak} of PCMs, window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and external shading ratio (ESR). (a) Enthalpy curves of PCMs for four T_{peak} levels, modeled using Eq. 5; (b)–(d): Example building configurations with varying WWR and ESR values — Design 75 (WWR = 50%, ESR = 67%), Design 39 (WWR = 90%, ESR = 67%), and Design 8 (WWR = 30%, ESR = 100%).

3.4. Calculation of the PCM effectiveness indicators

The PCM effectiveness indicators were calculated using Eq. 1. For this, the daily loads saved, $DLS(i)$, by the incorporation of PCMs into the building were calculated as the difference between the daily load of the Baseline model and the daily loads of its corresponding PCM model, as described in Eq. 2. The daily heating and cooling ideal loads were directly obtained from EnergyPlus for each design and studied climate, and the total daily loads were computed as a sum of them.

Regarding the calculation of the latent heat storage capacity LSC installed in the building using PCMs, it was obtained as:

$$LSC = \Delta h_{PCM} * (m_{PCM1} + m_{PCM2}), \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta h_{PCM}=210000$ J/kg, and the mass of PCM layers are calculated as:

$$m_{\text{PCM1}} = \rho * \text{THK}_{\text{PCM1}} * \text{Area}_{\text{PCM1}},$$

$$m_{\text{PCM2}} = \rho * \text{THK}_{\text{PCM2}} * \text{Area}_{\text{PCM2}},$$

where $\rho = 880 \text{ kg/m}^3$, THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2} varying according to the sample, $\text{Area}_{\text{PCM2}} = 48 \text{ m}^2$, and $\text{Area}_{\text{PCM1}} = \text{TotalArea}_{\text{wall}} - \text{Area}_{\text{window}}$.

Therefore, for all the building designs in the Morris sample, the PCMEI was calculated separately for the total loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Total}}$), heating loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Heating}}$), and cooling loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Cooling}}$) to analyze them.

4. Results

This section describes and discusses the results obtained from the sensitivity analysis. Furthermore, the relationships between the building thermal load reductions and PCMEIs were studied to better understand the behavior of the new indicators. The research dataset of this work, which includes all the EnergyPlus models and results obtained, is openly available in [43], for closer analysis (or reproduction).

4.1. Sensitivity analysis of the PCMEIs

The Morris method [34] produces three indices: the mean (μ), the mean of absolute values (μ^*), and the standard deviation (σ). The μ^* index represents the overall influence or importance of an input variable on the output, with higher μ^* values indicating stronger and more consistent effects. The σ index, on the other hand, quantifies the variability of the elementary effects and therefore reflects the degree of nonlinearity or interaction between variables. Large σ values suggest that a variable's impact depends on the levels of other parameters or on nonlinear response behavior, whereas low σ values indicate predominantly linear and independent effects. Following established recommendations [44], we compute μ^* and σ and normalize each by the within-climate maximum to enable consistent comparison of influence and interaction strength across PCMEIs.

Fig. 6 shows the Morris sensitivity results across the studied climates, illustrating the relative influence of design variables on the proposed indicators. For clarity, only the results for $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Total}}$ are presented and discussed here, while those for $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Heating}}$ and $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Cooling}}$ are provided in Appendix A.

The results reveal consistent patterns across the four analyzed climates. The *window-to-wall ratio* (WWR) and the *PCM quantity* (represented by THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}) are the most influential variables for all indicators— $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Heating}}$, $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Cooling}}$, and $\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Total}}$. These parameters govern the magnitude and timing of heat gains and determine the available latent storage capacity within thermal zone.

External shading (ESR) shows intermediate influence, especially for heating and total conditions, as it moderates direct solar gains that activate PCM melting and solidification cycles. In contrast, the *wall insulation thickness* (THK_{INS}) and the *PCM melting temperatures* ($\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$ and $\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$) exhibit the lowest sensitivity across climates. This finding challenges the common assumption that melting tempera-

ture dominates PCM performance; at the whole-building-level, envelope geometry and PCM mass exert far stronger control.

Overall, these results confirm that PCM effectiveness in buildings is primarily driven by the interaction between passive solar design parameters and the total installed latent capacity, rather than by detailed material properties. This reinforces the importance of integrating PCM selection and envelope design early in the building design process to maximize whole-building-level performance.

Fig. 6: Morris sensitivity analysis of PCMEI_{Total} for four ASHRAE climate zones: (a) 3A, (b) 4A, (c) 5A, and (d) 6A. Symbols denote the analyzed design variables: wall PCM thickness (THK_{PCM1}), roof PCM thickness (THK_{PCM2}), PCM peak melting temperatures (T_{peakPCM1}, T_{peakPCM2}), wall insulation thickness (THK_{INS}), window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and external shading ratio (ESR). The indices μ^* and σ represent the overall influence and the degree of nonlinearity or interaction, respectively.

To further examine PCM effectiveness, Fig. 7 presents the box plots of PCMEI_{Total}, PCMEI_{Heating}, and

PCMEI_{Cooling} across the four analyzed climates. Several consistent statistical patterns are observed. Overall, PCM effectiveness increases with climate cooling dominance: the lowest values occur in Climate 3A, while the highest appear in Climate 6A. Median PCMEI_{Total} values range from approximately 2% to 4%, with maxima reaching 10–15% in colder climates (5A and 6A), where larger temperature swings enhance PCM activation. A similar trend is observed for the upper extremes, with maximum PCMEI_{Total} values of about 7% for Climate 3A, 15% for Climates 4A and 5A, and 22% for Climate 6A. Notably, PCM effectiveness increases for the non-dominant thermal load: PCMEI_{Cooling} tends to be higher in heating-dominated climates (e.g., 6A), while PCMEI_{Heating} performs better in more cooling- or balanced-dominated climates, such as 4A.

No negative PCMEI values were observed, confirming that PCM integration—when melting temperatures are aligned with HVAC setpoints—does not deteriorate building performance.

Fig. 7: Distribution of PCMEI values for total, heating, and cooling effectiveness across four representative ASHRAE climates: (a) 3A, (b) 4A, (c) 5A, and (d) 6A. Boxes represent interquartile ranges, with markers showing mean values and circles denoting outliers.

4.2. Impact on the building annual thermal loads

To better interpret the PCMEI results, Fig. 8 compares the total load reductions obtained from PCM integration with the corresponding PCMEI_{Total} values for the four analyzed climates. Regarding the load reductions, each point represents the performance of a PCM-integrated design relative to its baseline (non-PCM) configuration.

Across all climates, an inverse tendency emerges: designs achieving the largest relative load reductions (up to 40–45%) often exhibit low PCMEI_{Total} values (below 5%), whereas configurations with the highest PCM effectiveness (up to 20–22%) show more moderate load reductions (10–20%). This pattern indicates that minimizing thermal loads and maximizing PCM utilization are not concurrent optimization goals. While some favorable envelope–PCM combinations or climatic conditions can substantially reduce energy use when PCM is incorporated, they may underactivate the material’s latent storage capacity. Conversely, higher PCMEI values occur in designs where the PCM undergoes frequent and complete phase transitions, even if the overall load reduction is smaller. These results confirm that PCMEI offers complementary insight to traditional energy-based metrics by quantifying the *efficiency of latent energy utilization* rather than the magnitude of PCM-driven load savings.

Fig. 8: Relationship between total annual load reduction (PCM versus baseline) and PCMEI_{Total} across four ASHRAE climates: (a) 3A, (b) 4A, (c) 5A, and (d) 6A.

Fig. 9 examines the relationship between PCM effectiveness (PCMEIs) and the absolute annual heating, cooling, and total loads of the PCM-integrated designs. A clear trade-off emerges across all climates: the most energy-efficient buildings (i.e., those with the lowest annual loads) display relatively low PCM effectiveness, whereas designs with higher loads show greater PCMEI values. For instance, in heating-dominated climates (e.g., 6A), PCMEI_{Heating} values up to 22% are associated with annual heating loads of 80–120 kWh/m², whereas highly insulated designs with loads below 25 kWh/m² exhibit PCMEI_{Heating} below 3%. A similar

pattern is observed for cooling, where the highest $PCMEI_{Cooling}$ values occur at moderate cooling demands.

Fig. 9: Relationship between PCMEI values and absolute annual thermal loads across four ASHRAE climates. Panels (a–d) show $PCMEI_{Total}$ versus total loads, (e–h) show $PCMEI_{Heating}$ versus heating loads, and (i–l) show $PCMEI_{Cooling}$ versus cooling loads for Climates 3A, 4A, 5A, and 6A, respectively.

These results demonstrate that PCMs are most effectively utilized in lower thermal-performance buildings—when the thermal demand is sufficient to drive frequent phase transitions but not so large that the PCM’s latent capacity becomes saturated. Hence, maximizing PCM utilization and minimizing total energy use are inherently competing design objectives. Building designers should therefore pursue a multi-objective approach to identify configurations that balance both criteria. Overall, these findings confirm that PCM effectiveness depends jointly on material activation and the magnitude of the building’s thermal demand.

4.3. Practical design guidelines using PCMEI

This section discusses how to use PCMEIs to inform PCM sizing and envelope decisions. Fig. 10 relates $PCMEI_{Total}$ to the ratio between the installed latent heat storage capacity (LSC) and the *Baseline* (no-PCM) maximum daily total load (MDTL). Across climates 3A–6A, $PCMEI_{Total}$ generally declines as $LSC/MDTL_{Baseline}$ increases, indicating diminishing utilization with oversizing. Higher PCMEI values are concentrated when the capacity ratio lies $\leq 2 \times$ the $MDTL_{Baseline}$; ratios well above this band rarely improve PCMEI.

From these patterns, we propose the following practical guideline for design:

1. **Establish the reference load.** Run a baseline (no-PCM) simulation of the target design and record the *maximum daily total load*, $MDTL_{baseline}$ (per season if needed).
2. **Constrain latent capacity.** Allocate PCM such that $LSC \leq 2 \times MDTL_{Baseline}$.
3. **Co-optimize envelope and PCM variables.** Adjust envelope parameters (e.g., WWR, external shading ratio, insulation thickness) together with PCM-related choices (quantity, placement, melting temperature) to *maximize* PCMEI while *minimizing* thermal loads. Use $PCMEI_{Heating}$ and $PCMEI_{Cooling}$ to target season-specific performance or multi-PCM uses.
4. **Integrate passive strategies.** In cooling-dominated climates—where PCM effectiveness can be limited—combine with other passive measures (e.g., night ventilation/free cooling) to enhance cycling.

5. Discussion

This study introduced the phase change material effectiveness indicators (PCMEIs) as physics-informed, whole-building-level metrics to objectively quantify the contribution of PCMs to building energy performance. By relating thermal-load savings to the installed latent capacity, the indicators isolate PCM utilization efficiency from absolute energy reductions, enabling transparent comparison across climates and envelope configurations. The multi-climate simulations and sensitivity analyses demonstrate that PCMEIs capture the fundamental interactions between PCM properties, building design parameters, and climate-driven boundary conditions.

The global sensitivity analysis identified the window-to-wall ratio (WWR), PCM thickness (representing installed quantity), and external shading ratio (ESR) as the dominant variables influencing PCM effectiveness across all climates. In contrast, PCM melting temperature and wall insulation thickness exhibited comparatively minor influence. These results challenge the conventional assumption that PCM melting temperature

Fig. 10: $PCMEI_{Total}$ versus the ratio of installed PCM capacity to the *baseline* (no-PCM) maximum daily total load across climates (3A–6A). The vertical line marks unity; higher PCMEI values concentrate below a threshold $2 \times MDTL_{Baseline}$.

is the primary design variable, revealing instead that building-envelope geometry and solar-gain management govern the extent to which latent capacity can be effectively activated. This finding emphasizes that PCM integration should be treated as part of a holistic envelope design strategy rather than as an isolated material property optimization.

The statistical distributions of PCMEIs (Fig. 7) indicate modest median effectiveness levels—typically between 2% and 4%—with maximum values of 10–15% in colder climates. These results align with the realistic performance expected under dynamic building operation, where perfect PCM cycling rarely occurs. In practice, PCMEIs represent theoretical utilization indicators: they assume that the entire latent capacity is potentially available for load reduction. However, when the PCM quantity is sufficient to meet the peak daily load of the year, a portion of the material inevitably remains inactive on milder days or during seasons with smaller temperature amplitudes. As a result, a consistent fraction of the PCM capacity is underutilized, even under ideal design conditions. This inherent mismatch highlights the need for defining benchmark PCMEI ranges that represent typical or achievable performance levels for different climates, building typologies, and control strategies. Establishing such benchmarks would provide context for interpreting PCMEI results, distinguishing between physically expected limitations and design-related inefficiencies.

The relationship between PCMEI values and absolute thermal loads (Fig. 9) reveals a clear trade-off: the most energy-efficient buildings, characterized by low thermal loads, display limited PCM activation, whereas higher-load designs achieve greater PCM utilization. PCMs are most effective in moderate-demand scenarios—where temperature oscillations are large enough to induce frequent phase transitions but not so high that latent capacity becomes saturated. Thus, minimizing thermal loads and maximizing PCM utilization represent inherently competing objectives. Rather than combining these effects into a synthetic index, this study treats them separately to provide a more transparent and physically interpretable evaluation framework. The results reinforce that PCM integration should be pursued through multi-objective design methods, balancing energy savings, material use, and cost-effectiveness.

Beyond these performance trade-offs, the PCMEI framework also provides direct guidance for practical PCM sizing and integration. As discussed in Section 4.3, PCM effectiveness tends to plateau once the installed latent storage capacity exceeds roughly twice the baseline maximum daily total load, highlighting a clear upper limit for efficient utilization. This relationship suggests that oversizing PCMs offers diminishing returns, as additional capacity remains largely uncycled under typical climatic variations. The results therefore reinforce the value of capacity-based design constraints and co-optimization of envelope and PCM parameters. Moreover, the higher PCMEI values observed for non-dominant loads (e.g., cooling in heating-dominated climates) indicate that strategic PCM deployment can complement other passive strategies, such as shading control or night ventilation, to enhance activation frequency and whole-building performance.

The consistent sensitivity patterns across climates confirm that the proposed indicators are robust and generalizable. They highlight that whole-building-level variables—such as envelope composition, solar aperture, and PCM quantity—dominate over detailed material parameters. Therefore, research efforts aimed at improving PCM-based building performance should prioritize integrated design optimization rather than isolated material enhancement. The framework presented here offers a replicable basis for comparing PCM strategies under diverse climatic and typological conditions, supporting decision-making in both early-stage design and retrofit analysis.

While the present study focused on lightweight, single-zone models, the PCMEI formulation is inherently scalable. Because it is expressed as a ratio of load reduction to installed latent capacity, it can be extended to multi-zone or high-mass buildings and incorporated into urban-scale simulation workflows. Future work should explore PCM performance under dynamic operational control, adaptive ventilation, and hybrid passive-active systems, as well as develop standardized PCMEI benchmarks for realistic performance ranges. These benchmarks would support practical adoption by providing reference values for expected PCM utilization under different conditions and enabling consistent comparison across studies.

By defining PCM performance through measurable, comparable indicators, this study establishes a foundation for a performance-driven, physics-based approach to latent thermal storage in buildings. PCMEIs enable objective quantification of PCM utilization efficiency independent of building size, typology, or climate. They also offer a potential framework for developing standardized metrics in building energy codes and certification schemes. Ultimately, this approach promotes more efficient, data-driven PCM deployment, advancing the role of thermal storage in achieving net-zero energy and climate-resilient buildings.

6. Limitations and future work

The present study provides a physics-informed and whole-building-level framework for evaluating PCM utilization in buildings; however, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, only two material-level variables—the melting temperature and latent storage capacity—were considered. While these parameters capture the dominant thermal behavior of commercial PCMs, other factors such as subcooling, anisotropic properties, or encapsulation effects were not explicitly modeled. Although we believe these phenomena are not highly influential for PCM effectiveness at the whole-building-level, incorporating them would enable a more comprehensive assessment of PCM performance, particularly for advanced composite or active systems.

Second, the analysis was conducted on a simplified single-zone lightweight prototype, intended to represent a generic building cell. Although this approach isolates fundamental interactions between envelope parameters and PCM performance, it does not capture the complexity of multi-zone dynamics, internal heat transfer between spaces, or realistic occupancy and control patterns. Future work should apply the proposed PCMEI framework to more detailed building archetypes and calibrated case studies to validate its applicability to real-world designs.

Third, the study relied exclusively on simulation-based analysis using the ENERGYPLUS PCM model, which has been experimentally validated in previous research. Nevertheless, direct experimental verification of the PCMEI framework would be valuable to confirm its robustness under measured operating conditions and to refine benchmark ranges for different climates and material configurations.

Finally, the comfort model was based on a dual setpoint strategy with no unmet hours, ensuring that all load variations directly reflect envelope-PCM interactions. Although appropriate for performance benchmarking, future work should couple the PCMEI framework with dynamic comfort or adaptive temperature models to explore PCM impacts under occupant-driven control or free-running conditions. Overall, extending the PCMEI methodology to multi-zone, experimentally calibrated, and control-integrated contexts will enhance its robustness and practical applicability. Such developments would facilitate the definition of standardized benchmark values, supporting the broader adoption of PCM-based latent storage in performance-driven building design and regulation.

7. Conclusions

This study introduced physics-informed Phase Change Material Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs) to objectively quantify the whole-building-level utilization of passive PCMs to building energy performance. Through whole-building EnergyPlus simulations and global sensitivity analysis, it was demonstrated that envelope design variables—particularly the window-to-wall ratio (WWR) and PCM quantity—exert a stronger influence on PCM effectiveness than material properties such as melting temperature. Despite substantial thermal load reductions, practical PCMEI values remained below 22%, reflecting the inherent limitations of PCM utilization under annually dynamic operational conditions.

Beyond the evaluation of individual designs, PCMEIs establish a scalable, physics-grounded framework for systematically optimizing latent thermal energy storage across diverse building types and climates. By

linking thermal-load savings to installed PCM capacity, the indicators enable performance-based decision-making, support early-stage design optimization, and facilitate the development of objective benchmarks for PCM integration. Their formulation allows consistent application across heating, cooling, and mixed-load scenarios, offering a unified evaluation tool for multi-objective sustainable building strategies.

The findings also yield actionable design insights. PCM effectiveness tends to plateau once the installed latent-capacity ratio exceeds roughly twice the building’s peak daily load, suggesting that oversizing offers diminishing returns. Incorporating PCMEIs into design workflows can therefore guide balanced envelope–PCM co-optimization and promote synergy with passive strategies such as shading control or night ventilation.

Importantly, the results highlight the need to define benchmark PCMEI ranges to contextualize theoretical effectiveness under realistic building operations. Since a portion of the PCM capacity remains inherently unutilized on milder days or during off-peak seasons, benchmark values would help differentiate expected physical limitations from suboptimal design outcomes. Developing such reference ranges for various climates and building typologies represents a key next step toward standardizing PCM assessment and comparison.

Looking forward, the broader deployment of PCMEIs could accelerate the integration of passive latent storage technologies into urban energy planning, demand-side management, and resilience strategies. As cities worldwide pursue scalable pathways toward net-zero energy goals, systematic indicators such as PCMEIs will be essential to unlock the full potential of phase change materials—not as isolated material innovations, but as integral components of climate-adaptive, low-carbon, and resilient built environments.

Data availability

The research data achieved in this work, including all the results and EnergyPlus models, can be found at Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17456055>) for closer analysis (or reproduction).

Appendix A. Extended results

To complement the main analysis, this section presents additional graphical results illustrating the detailed behavior of the PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs) and their sensitivity to design parameters across the analyzed ASHRAE climate zones. These figures provide extended evidence supporting the main findings discussed in Section 4, emphasizing the consistency of the PCMEI framework under both heating and cooling conditions.

Fig. A.11: Morris sensitivity analysis of PCMEI_{Heating} and PCMEI_{Cooling} for four ASHRAE climate zones: (a) 3A, (b) 4A, (c) 5A, and (d) 6A. Symbols denote the analyzed design variables: wall PCM thickness (THK_{PCM1}), roof PCM thickness (THK_{PCM2}), PCM peak melting temperatures (T_{peakPCM1}, T_{peakPCM2}), wall insulation thickness (THK_{INS}), window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and external shading ratio (ESR).

Fig. A.12: Relationship between total annual thermal-load reduction (PCM-integrated versus baseline design) and PCMEI_{Total} for four ASHRAE climate zones: (a) 3A, (b) 4A, (c) 5A, and (d) 6A.

Declaration of Interest statement

The authors declare no competing interests.

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